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Title: Acoustic cue weighting in the perception of Spanish intonation contrasts: Differences between tonal and non-tonal language listeners.

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Abstract

Previous research shows that listeners from different language backgrounds may use multiple acoustic cues differently to identify phonemic contrasts and sound changes. However, less is known about the cue weighting differences between tonal and non-tonal languages in the perception of intonation. This study aims to fill this gap by examining how native listeners of Chinese and Spanish use three acoustic cues (i.e., f₀, duration, and intensity) to perceive question-statement contrasts in Spanish. Two identification tests are carried out using synthesized stimuli where the f₀ contour co-varies with duration or intensity in sentence-final syllables. While changes in the three acoustic properties significantly affect Spanish listeners' performance, Chinese speakers are only sensitive to the modulation of f₀ and duration. Crucially, this sensitivity to f₀ and duration cues is higher for Spanish listeners, although they require significantly higher f₀ ranges for perceiving questions than Chinese speakers. Moreover, the trade-off between primary and secondary cues suggests that the perception of intonation is a dynamic process during which listeners can take advantage of the co-variations of multiple cues to help recognize the intended phonological category. Beyond acoustic effects, the intonation perception is mainly influenced by native language experience but modulated by individual differences and stress patterns.

Keywords

Intonation perception, acoustic cue weighting, tonal and non-tonal languages, phonetic trading relation, individual differences

Declarations of interest

None.

Acoustic cue weighting in the perception of Spanish intonation contrasts: Differences between tonal and non-tonal language listeners

1.0 Introduction

Intonation, a suprasegmental feature of speech, can be used for several purposes, such as signaling sentence types (i.e., question vs. statement) and focusing differences (i.e., broad vs. narrow focus) in a linguistically structured way (Ladd, 1996; Levis, 1999) and conveying emotional and attitudinal meanings (i.e., surprise, anger, and irony) in the sociocultural-oriented interface between prosody and pragmatics (Rodero, 2011; Wichmann & Blakemore, 2006). In either case, intonation is realized using multidimensional acoustic properties. The continuous values along each acoustic dimension can be used as cues by listeners to recognize a particular linguistic category (c.f. Kong & Edwards, 2016; Kuang & Cui, 2018, 2019; Peng et al., 2012; Toscano & McMurray, 2010). While listeners can take advantage of multiple acoustic cues to specify the best exemplar of linguistic categories, the contribution or weight of these cues makes a difference to their judgments because listeners' attention is selective (Clayards, 2018; Holt & Lotto, 2006; Kuang & Cui, 2018; Tillman et al., 2017; Toscano & McMurray, 2010).

Moreover, cross-linguistic research shows that listeners from different language backgrounds may differ in the cue weighting for a phonological contrast (c.f. Dmitrieva, 2019 for stop voicing contrast by native and Russian learners of English; Hattori & Iverson, 2005 for /r/-/l/ contrasts by native and Japanese learners of English; Lee et al., 2013 for voiceless stops by speakers of two Korean dialects), given the influence of their previous linguistic experience and native phonetic and phonological conventions. Nonetheless, most cue weighting studies have focused on the perception of segmental features between first (L1) and second (L2) language speakers of English, leaving other language pairs far less explored in the suprasegmental domain. Therefore, this study attempts to bridge the gap by examining how L1 and Chinese L2 speakers of Spanish—a new pairing between tonal and non-tonal languages—rely on multiple acoustic cues to perceive Spanish intonation contrasts and how these cues are combined and interacted during listeners' perceptual process.

1.1 Multiple cue weighting in intonation perception

The question-statement contrast can be encoded by several resources other than intonation contours. For instance, in Peninsular Spanish, yes-no questions differ from statements in word order: while statements follow the subject-verb-object order, the order of questions is often verb-subject-object (Haverkate, 2006). In Mandarin Chinese, the best-known characteristic of yes-no questions is the presence of a final particle *ma* (Yuan, 2011). Although syntactic or lexical mechanisms can encode sentence types, intonation alone can achieve the same effect. Questions that differ from statements only in the intonation contour are known as “intonation questions,” which are of particular interest for this study.

Like other perceptual domains, multiple sources of information must be combined in intonation perception. One instance of this situation is that normal-hearing English listeners can use variations in fundamental frequency (f_0), intensity, and duration to identify question-statement contrasts depending on listening conditions (i.e., full-spectrum vs. spectrally degraded), stimulus type (i.e., naturally produced stimuli vs. resynthesized stimuli), and the chronological age of the participants (Peng et al., 2012). Similar integration of multiple cues for perceiving intonation categories has been observed in native listeners of Mandarin Chinese (Yuan, 2006), Cantonese (Ma et al., 2008, 2011), German (Niebuhr, 2007), and South Korean (Chang, 2013). However, Lieberman (1967) noted that most English listeners could effectively recognize the difference between questions and statements based solely on the f_0 contour during the final 150 to 200 ms of the utterance. Face (2005, 2007) provided parallel experimental evidence for Madrid Spanish, where the final pitch movement was the most reliable cue for signaling the

question-statement contrasts that could override any previous contradictory cue. The importance of f0 pitch as the main cue for questionhood encoding is also confirmed in Bolinger (1978). By surveying roughly 250 languages, the author revealed that 70% of human languages use a final pitch rise to mark questions, while the rest may rely on the increase of the overall pitch level for question encoding (Bolinger, 1978). Spanish is a good example of the first kind of language. By contrast, Mandarin Chinese, a typical tonal language, corresponds to the second case and differs from intonational languages in exhibiting a tone-dependent intonation mechanism. That is, provided there is no particle at the end of sentences, the lexical tone type of the final word can influence intonation in Chinese. For instance, Yuan (2006, 2011) showed that the question intonation in Chinese was perceived more accurately by L1 listeners if the utterance-final tone was falling (Tone4); it was harder to recognize if there was a rising tone at the end (Tone2).

Although intonation is perceived primarily as a function of the f0 modulation in tonal and non-tonal languages, other secondary cues such as duration and intensity can also influence listeners' judgments by conveying important but less reliable acoustical information (Ortega-Llebaria et al., 2017). Feng et al. (2019) reported that the increase of duration and intensity values in the sentence-final word significantly contributed to the likelihood that a given sentence was perceived as a question in American English. A similar duration and intensity effect is expected in the two language groups examined in this study since intonation questions in Spanish and Chinese are reported to have a longer duration and a higher intensity in the vocalic part of the sentence-final word (c.f. Romera Barrios et al., 2007 for Barcelona Spanish; Yuan, 2006 for Mandarin Chinese). However, the perceptual weighting of these acoustic cues (i.e., f0, duration, and intensity) may not be identical between L1 and L2 listeners from different language backgrounds. Studies supporting this notion are that Chinese learners of English could use the intensity of the final word as a secondary cue to signal question-statement contrasts in English, whereas English L1 speakers ignored the intensity changes when the f0 contour was strongly represented (Morrow & Liu, 2013). This finding for native English listeners accords with Peng et al. (2012) but contrasts with Feng et al. (2019), who reported that English L1 listeners were significantly affected by the duration and intensity variations in question-statement recognition, whereas Chinese L2 learners were not. Although it remains unclear why such studies reached different results with the same experimental approach, the small samples used in their research (5 and 14 participants, respectively) may minimize the strength of their conclusions.

1.2 Debate on the tonal language benefit in f0 perception

Given that Mandarin Chinese is a tonal language, its native speakers are exposed intensively to f0 modulations at the lexical tone and sentence-intonation level (Liu & Pell, 2012). The strong informational emphasis of f0 pitch in Mandarin often raises the question of whether Chinese listeners have enhanced behavioral sensitivity to the processing of pitch events than speakers of a non-tonal language. Chang et al. (2017) indicated that Mandarin listeners had a higher identification rate of high-variability Cantonese-level tones than English listeners because they had more exposure to lexical tones. Deroche et al. (2019), Ortega-Llebaria et al. (2017), and Xu et al. (2006) showed that Chinese listeners had a higher sensitivity to f0 direction changes in English words and detected f0 mismatches more rapidly than non-tonal language listeners. Similar benefits have also been reported in Bidelman et al. (2013), where tonal language (Cantonese) listeners and musicians share enhanced perceptual and cognitive abilities in lower-level pitch perception, thereby outperforming English speakers in processing the f0 information necessary for basic auditory and music perceptions. Even though these studies reported parallel findings, the hypothesis that speaking a tonal language increases listeners' sensitivity to pitch perception is still an ongoing debate. For instance, Chien et al. (2020), Liang and Heuven (2007), So and Best (2010), and Tsukada (2018) provided counterexamples to this hypothesis by showing that speakers with tone language experience were not necessarily superior in perceiving non-native lexical tones or native intonation contrasts than non-tonal language listeners.

A possible explanation for the inconsistent results based on the literature may be that the pitch enhancement exhibited by tonal language listeners depends on the internal f_0 representation of the stimuli and may not generalize to all pitch dimensions. The f_0 advantage of tonal language listeners is more likely present in perception tasks, where pitch information is processed in a manner consistent with the auditory demands of their native tone language (Bidelman et al., 2013; Deroche et al., 2019; Krishnan et al., 2009). This notion was demonstrated by the finding that the higher discrimination ability of Cantonese listeners in perceiving large pitch incongruences disappeared when perceiving subtle pitch deviations smaller than the f_0 differences between Cantonese-level tones (Bidelman et al., 2013). Relative to the lexical tone perception, the higher and incompatible pitch processing ability required by the fine-grained f_0 perception may account for the absence of tonal language benefit in this situation. Similarly, the lack of f_0 sensitivity among Chinese listeners in some prior perception works can be attributed to that the auditory skills necessary for curvilinear Mandarin tones are not entirely compatible with the expertise required for perceiving discrete music-level tones and linear intonation patterns. Thus, the f_0 advantage of tonal language speakers is limited to linguistically relevant features of their native pitch events to which they have broader experience, such as dynamic f_0 contrastive patterns with particular curvatures and direction changes (Deroche et al., 2019).

Further neurobehavioral findings support the notion of a tonal language benefit under specific pitch dimensions by demonstrating that the neural substrates engaged for processing the higher- and lower-level pitch are different during perception (Doherty et al., 2004; Gandour, 2009; Zatorre & Gandour, 2008). More crucially, Chien et al. (2020) reported that listeners from tonal and non-tonal languages had cross-linguistic commonalities and dissociations in f_0 processing depending on the type of the perceived pitch events. Consistent with Friederici (2011) and Kreitewolf et al. (2014), Chien et al. (2020) revealed that pitch perceived as lexical tone overlapped with intonation in left-brain regions, in Mandarin and German listeners, but evoked an additional semantic area for tonal language speakers only. By contrast, pitch processed as intonation activated bilateral brain areas and was generalized to tonal and non-tonal language listeners, regardless of their language-specific realization of intonation. Thus, in other words, the results indicated that the neural enhancement of pitch encoding exhibited by tonal language speakers is present only in the perception of contrastive tone patterns, but not in the prosodic evaluation of intonation categories at the sentence level.

In addition, the potential f_0 conflicts in the tone-dependent intonation system of Chinese might explain the cross-linguistic differences in pitch perception. Unlike intonational languages that use pitch primarily to signal intonation, the f_0 contours in Chinese have dual linguistic functions that can convey lexical tone and sentential intonation meanings (Lin, 2018). Thus, Chinese listeners may experience more challenges in intonation processing when f_0 is used simultaneously to encode information of the two dimensions (Yuan, 2011). Liang and Heuven (2007) provided supportive evidence for this view by showing that Mandarin L1 listeners were less sensitive to intonation but more sensitive to lexical tones than L2 speakers of a non-tonal language. This result has been attributed to that f_0 is primarily perceived at the lexical level for tonal language listeners, including their longer processing times and reduced sensitivity to pitch perceived at the sentence-intonation level (Liang & Heuven, 2007). Similar findings are also observed in Chen (2005) and Gussenhoven and Chen (2000), where listeners of non-tonal languages (Dutch and Hungarian) were more effective than Chinese speakers in using prosodic differences for the question-statement identification of nonsense stimuli because they were less bothered by the lexical tone interference. However, current studies on whether tonal language experience increases listeners' behavioral sensitivity to dynamic pitch perceived as intonation remain controversial. Unlike the prior cited studies, Feng et al. (2019) posited that Mandarin L2 speakers of English were more sensitive than L1 speakers to f_0 linear changes perceived in English question-statement intonation categories. The conclusions remain to be elucidated due to the small sample size in their experiment.

1.3 *The dynamic properties of speech perception*

Speech perception is a dynamic process in which multiple sources of cues are integrated to help recognize intended linguistic targets. Understanding how these cues are combined and interacted during this process is often described using *phonetic trading relation*—a phenomenon in which the shift of values of one acoustic cue can be compensated by an opposing change of another cue such that the phonological category is preserved (c.f. Repp, 1982 for more details). One instance of this trade-off relationship during intonation perception is that English L1 listeners increased their reliance on duration and intensity cues to compensate for the f_0 loss under spectrally degraded conditions (Peng et al., 2012). Similar compensatory behavior for the covarying cues has been observed in the perception of whispered speech (Jiao & Xu, 2019), and many coarticulatory processes, such as vowel nasalization (Beddor & Krakow, 1999), voicing on initial stops (Repp, 1982), and ongoing sound changes (c.f. tense vs. lax register in Kuang & Cui, 2018).

However, it is argued that the perceptual compensation exists only for listeners who are sensitive to both acoustical properties under trading relations (Hodgson & Miller, 1996). A direct test supporting this notion is that speakers with smaller just noticeable difference in F0 discrimination tasks (thus, higher perceptual acuity to F1) made greater acoustic compensations in response to F1 formant perturbations in English vowels (Villacorta et al., 2007). Similarly, Nault and Munhall (2020) detected a significant positive correlation between individual subjects' compensatory changes to real-time formant perturbations and their perceptual acuity evaluated by their discrimination performance on a vowel continuum. In the suprasegmental domain, little research has been conducted to examine the relationship between perception and compensations to prosodic variations. An indirect example of such could be that English L1 listeners who were more sensitive to duration and intensity modulations than Chinese L2 speakers used higher final f_0 contours to recognize questions, as an acoustic compensation for the weakened duration and intensity cues in certain experimental conditions (Feng et al., 2019). From the standpoint of prior compensation studies, English L1 listeners made larger responses to the trading relations between f_0 and duration (intensity) and therefore should correlate with higher sensitivity to these acoustical properties involved for the identification of intonation contrasts. Surprisingly, however, the findings of Feng et al. (2019) contradicted this hypothesis by showing that English L1 listeners were less sensitive than Chinese L2 learners to sentence-final f_0 linear changes. Given that the small sample size affects the reliability in Feng et al. (2019), parallel investigations are conducted in this work for the Chinese-Spanish language pair to test whether listeners' performance accords with the relationship between perceptual sensitivity and compensatory ability.

1.4 *Objectives and hypotheses*

The noted prior research focuses on the acoustic processing of intonation and tone by native English listeners and non-native Chinese speakers. Thus far, no study examines the perceptual weighing of the acoustic cues in the perception of Peninsular Spanish intonation between native speakers and non-native listeners whose L1 is Mandarin Chinese. Thus, this study primarily investigates how listeners of the two languages use f_0 , duration, and intensity cues to perceive the question-statement contrast in Spanish. We focus on a) whether listeners' perception of Spanish intonation contrasts is influenced by changes in the three acoustic cues and b) which language group is more sensitive to the f_0 , duration, and intensity modulations in sentence-final syllables. Moreover, prior studies show that individual features such as age and gender may affect speech perception by fine-tuning listeners' perceptual ability and pragmatic skills (Bishop et al., 2020; Patel & Grigos, 2006; Ryalls et al., 1994). Hence, this study c) examines to which extent listeners' perception performance is predicted by their L1, age, and gender. Accordingly, we designed two perceptual experiments in which stimuli were synthesized by manipulating the values of the three acoustic parameters.

Given prior neurobehavioral findings (Chien et al., 2020), we hypothesize that tonal (Chinese) and non-tonal (Spanish) language listeners have a similar sensitivity to the f_0 contours perceived as intonation because they shared a general bilateral network for intonation processing. However, relative to listeners of a non-tonal language, we hypothesize that Chinese speakers may use lower f_0 contours to recognize Spanish questions than Spanish listeners given the influence of language-specific intonation categories (Feng et al., 2019; Liu & Rodriguez, 2012). Following cue weighting studies in L1 and L2 English (e.g., Feng et al., 2019; Morrow & Liu, 2013; Peng et al., 2012), we also hypothesize that the perception of Spanish sentence types could be influenced by changes in secondary cues (i.e., duration and intensity), on which native Spanish listeners would rely on more heavily than non-native Chinese speakers. Finally, in addition to L1 background, we hypothesize that individual features (e.g., age and gender) affect listeners' performance during question-statement identification.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Stimuli creation

The intonation of Spanish yes-no questions and broad focus statements differs in the prenucleus and nucleus (Face, 2011; Face & Prieto, 2007). Since the focus of this study is the intonational nucleus, we used only sentences with a single stressed word as stimuli such that the prenucleus effect can be excluded. Each sentence comprised one trisyllabic word: *Sevilla* (penultimate syllable stress—paroxytone) and *Alcalá* (final syllable stress—oxytone). The original recordings of the two items were obtained using a discourse completion task (Félix-Brasdefer, 2010). A female native speaker of Peninsular Spanish (age at the recording: 31) was required to produce the two one-word sentences in a broad focus statement context. The speaker was required to speak at a normal rate. The recordings took place in a quiet room with the Rode Smartlav+ microphone connected to a Scarlett Solo interface. Speech files were digitized at a sampling rate of 44.1 kHz and with a quantization precision of 16 bits. The final syllable of two one-word sentences was chosen for the acoustic manipulation. The target stimuli were created by manipulating f_0 , duration, and intensity. Prior to the pitch manipulation, the non-final segments of the two one-word sentences were normalized at a 70 dB sound pressure level and further used as a reference for the parametric variation of intensity in Experiment 2.

2.1.1 F_0 manipulation

The f_0 contour of the word-final syllable was replaced by a multi-step f_0 continuum using the “to manipulation” function in *Praat* (Boersma & Weenink, 2020). The pitch contour of the last syllable was stylized into two pitch points (defined as A1 and A2), and the values in between were defined by interpolation (Zarate-Sandez et al., 2015). As shown in Fig. 1, the start point A1 was fixed at the beginning of the final syllable's vowel, keeping the pitch height as in the original sentence. Thus, the f_0 value of A1 for *Alcalá* and *Sevilla* was 196 Hz and 200 Hz, respectively. The endpoint A2 was anchored at the last regular glottal pulse observed in the spectrogram and had an f_0 value nearly identical to A1 (3 Hz difference). The f_0 continuum of A2 was manipulated nine times upward and once downward, with a 20 Hz step size (greater than the slightest pitch variation normal-hearing adults can perceive). The detailed manipulation values of the stimuli are given in the Appendix (Table X). Hence, 11 f_0 steps spanning over 200 Hz were generated for the final syllable of each word. The 22 f_0 contours (2 stress positions*11 f_0 steps) with different terminal pitches were further used as the basis for manipulating the duration and intensity.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the pitch manipulation in the oxytone word *Alcalá*. The start point A1 was 196 Hz. The endpoint A2 was manipulated from 176 Hz to 376 Hz, with a 20 Hz step size. The original duration of the final vowel (185 ms) was set as the medium duration for the stimulus *Alcalá*.

2.1.2 Duration manipulation

In Experiment 1, the 22 pitch stimuli described in the previous section were used to add a duration manipulation following a procedure similar to Feng et al. (2019). Three duration levels were established in the study: short, medium (i.e., original), and long. As shown in Fig. 1, the original vowel duration of the statement's last syllable was selected as the medium value for each word. The specific duration values of the stimuli at the three duration levels are given in the Appendix X. The long duration was created by incorporating *Praat* 50 ms from the center of the nucleus of the original vowel in the last syllable. The +50 ms value was used because previous acoustic findings of Spanish intonation show that the final vowel of yes-no questions was roughly 40–70 milliseconds longer per the stress type of the final word than that of statements (c.f. Romera Barrios et al., 2007 for the intonation analysis of Barcelona Spanish). The short duration was generated by removing 40 ms from the same vowel nucleus. The reduced value was defined by referring to the shortest production of a statement by the same Spanish speaker. Since each duration level was combined with 11 different pitch contours, the stimuli for Experiment 1 were 66 (2 stress positions*3 durational levels*11 f0 steps).

2.1.3 Intensity manipulation

In Experiment 2, the same set of 22 pitch contours in Section 3.1.1 were used to manipulate intensity. The intensity of the word-final syllable was synthesized using the “constant amplification” function in Cool Edit Pro 2.1 (Syntrillium Software Corporation, 2003). Three levels of intensity were created by applying -7 dB, 0 dB, and +7 dB respective changes to the final syllable vowel (c.f. schematic representations of the intensity manipulation in Appendix X). The manipulated values employed the normalized intensity of the non-final part of the sentence (70 dB, as in Section 3.1.1) as reference level. Hence, the low, medium (original), and high intensities were set at 63 dB, 70 dB, and 77 dB, respectively. Thus, Experiment 2 had 66 auditory stimuli (2 stress positions*3 intensity levels*11 f0 steps).

2.2 Procedure

Data of the perception tests were collected via an online survey, constructed electronically using the web-based software, *Alchemer*. The survey comprised three sections. The first section collected information on the socio-demographic and linguistic background of the participants. The second (third) section contained the 66 auditory stimuli of Experiment 1 (2). The survey was administered in each listener's preferred language (Chinese or Spanish). The stimulus order of each experiment was randomized, and the text of each stimulus was displayed on the screen

without punctuation marks. Listeners could participate in one or both experiments, depending on their interests. Those who chose to participate in one were randomly assigned to one of the two auditory experiments. They were required to listen to the stimuli using earphones in a quiet place. Moreover, listeners were instructed to listen to every stimulus once; however, they could listen to it a second time if the recording failed to play for technical reasons.

Prior to the experiments, participants performed practice trials to familiarize themselves with the procedure. The perceptual answers of the two experiments were arranged on a five-point Likert scale to capture listeners' perceptual changes more accurately. Listeners were tasked to identify which of the five descriptions of the sentence type was closer to the stimulus they just heard by selecting one of the following options: "Statement," "More statement than question," "Either statement or question," "More question than statement," and "Question." A short break was inserted after each section to compensate for fatigue.

2.3 Participants

48 Peninsular Spanish (hereafter, SN) speakers and 95 Mandarin Chinese (hereafter, CN) listeners participated in the survey. Data on two SN listeners aged over 60 were excluded. Moreover, data on CN listeners who started studying Spanish before age 16 were removed from the analysis to control for the effect of age of acquisition. Further, data on participants ($N = 5$) with an A1 or A2 proficiency level in Spanish were excluded because they hardly knew Spanish intonation. The rest of the CN speakers have an intermediate (B1), advanced (B2), or superior (C1) level of proficiency and confirmed that Peninsular Spanish was the language variety to which they had been predominantly exposed during the learning process.

Experiment 1 had 39 SN listeners and 78 CN speakers from 18 to 59 years of age ($N = 117$, 90 females, 28 males, $M_{age} = 28.27$, $SD = 8.43$). Experiment 2 had 33 SN listeners and 77 CN speakers from 19 to 58 years of age ($N = 110$, 84 females, 26 males, $M_{age} = 28.02$, $SD = 8.46$). No one reported any history of hearing or communication problems at the time of testing.

2.4 Statistical analysis

We conducted statistical analyses of data using R software (R Core Team, 2020). Since the two experiments' outcome variable was arranged on a five-point ordinal scale, proportional-odds logistic regression (POLR) was used to model the data. However, from the *Brant* test results, some explanatory variables in the POLR models rejected the parallel regression assumption. Hence, for the final estimates, we employed a more flexible ordered generalized linear model (OGLM) to relax the parallel lines assumption for variables where it is violated and allow every effect to have separate coefficients for the five levels of the dependent variable (Abrudan et al., 2020; Williams, 2016): statement (level 1), more statement than question (level 2), either statement or question (level 3), more question than statement (level 4), question (level 5).

Two OGLM models were built separately for the data of Experiments 1 and 2 using the *oglmx* package for R (Carroll, 2018). Stress Type (penultimate- vs. final-stress), L1 Group (CN vs. SN), and Gender (male vs. female) were included as binary predictors, while Duration (short < medium < long) and Intensity (63 dB < 70 dB < 77 dB) were treated as discrete ordinal variables. *f0* Change, Age, and Stimulus Order were included as continuous predictors, and the latter two were z-transformed and centered on their mean before entering the model.

A stepwise backward elimination was performed to get the best model fit. The *stepAIC* function from the *MASS* package was used to iteratively exclude the least contributive predictors of the model (Kassambara, 2018; Ripley et al., 2013). Predictors that failed to achieve the .05 level of significance were removed from the model until all factors were statistically significant for the prediction. Finally, all samples were randomly split into a training and testing set to examine the

statistical validity. The training set was constructed to estimate all the effects included in the model. The testing set was used to evaluate the testing error by computing the logarithmic (log) loss on the folds from the training set (Brown, 2020).

3.0 Results

3.1 Results of Experiment 1

The results of OGLM model fitted for Experiment 1 (see Table 1) revealed that listeners' perception of the five possible sentence types was significantly predicted by Stimulus Order [$\chi^2(1) = 7.73, p < .01$], Age [$\chi^2(1) = 60.13, p < .001$], Gender [$\chi^2(1) = 4.29, p < .05$], Stress Type [$\chi^2(1) = 78.60, p < .001$], and the three two-way interactions: L1 Group \times f0 Change [$\chi^2(1) = 28.05, p < .001$], L1 Group \times Duration [$\chi^2(2) = 28.15, p < .001$], and f0 Change \times Duration [$\chi^2(2) = 16.75, p < .001$]. Considering the effect of the f0 cue, Table 1 shows that a unit increase in the final f0 contour significantly decreased the likelihood of statement-like responses (i.e., levels 1 and 2) while increasing the possibility of question-like identifications (i.e., levels 4 and 5). However, confirming the general predictions, critical cross-linguistic differences emerged between the CN and SN groups on using the f0 pitch to perceive Spanish intonation categories.

As revealed by the L1 coefficients in Table 1, the first distinction is that CN listeners had a significantly greater likelihood than SN speakers to recognize a stimulus as a question-like sentence and needed lower terminal pitch values for question identifications. For instance, it is apparent in Fig. 2 that, when the terminal pitch was increased in 120 Hz, the most predicted sentence type of CN listeners was "question"; meanwhile, SN listeners needed a pitch rise greater than 140 Hz to make "question" the most predicted answer in the short and medium durations. One possible reason for these cross-linguistic differences in f0 use regards the three-way contrast of intonational phrase (IP)-final boundary tones in Peninsular Spanish. This language variety, apart from the low (L%) and high (H%) boundary tones, involves mid-level tones to signal uncertainty statements (!H%) and statements of obvious (L!H%) (Estebas-Vilaplana & Prieto, 2010). From native (SN) listeners' perspectives, both low- and mid-level tones correspond to the statement category (be they broad focus statements as in L% or epistemically biased statements as in !H% and L!H%). Thus, the lower likelihood of question-like responses showed by SN listeners is probably because they categorized the final mid-level pitch as a biased statement. By contrast, CN listeners may interpret it as a question because any tone (i.e., !H% or L!H%) not strictly low (i.e., L%) was perceived as high (i.e., H%), thereby relating to a question category.

Table 1. Summary of the marginal effects in the OGLM model, fitted for Experiment 1 (coefficients and *t*-stat. ****p* < 0.001; ***p* < 0.01; **p* < 0.05; ‘.’*p* < 0.1.)

Predictor	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Order	0.00381**	0.00928**	0.00391**	-0.01100**	-0.00600**
Age	-0.01241***	-0.03021***	-0.01271***	0.03581***	0.01954***
GenderFemale	-0.00640*	-0.01530*	-0.00607*	0.01818*	0.00959*
StressPenultimate	-0.01307***	-0.03171***	-0.01332***	0.03754***	0.02056***
L1SN	0.14632***	0.24241***	0.034729***	-0.28640***	-0.137064***
f0	-0.00210***	-0.00512***	-0.00216***	0.00607***	0.00331***
L1SN \times f0	-0.00026***	-0.00063***	-0.00027***	0.00075***	0.00041***
L1SN \times DurMedium	-0.01137*	-0.02892	-0.01466.	0.03386.	0.02064.
L1SN \times DurLong	-0.02868***	-0.07777***	-0.01420***	0.08662***	0.06755***
f0 \times DurMedium	-0.00006	-0.00014	-0.00006	0.00016	0.00009
f0 \times DurLong	-0.00023**	-0.00056**	-0.00024**	0.00066**	0.00036**

Note: Levels 1–5, in order, signify the five possible responses in the perception test: statement, more statement than question, either statement or question, more question than statement, question.

Fig. 2. Effect displays between L1 Group, f0 Change, and Duration for each response level, holding constant all other variables in Experiment 1.

The second difference between CN and SN listeners is that the effect of f0 pitch on the perception of sentence types was strongly affected by listeners' L1 background. The estimated coefficients for the interaction between L1 Group \times f0 Change at the five response levels (Table 1) indicated that the slope for the question-statement identification on f0 change was significantly steeper for SN listeners than CN speakers. Contrary to prior assumptions, this finding seems to suggest that SN listeners were more sensitive than CN speakers to f0 modulations perceived as intonation.

Moreover, the significant interaction between L1 Group \times Duration showed that CN and SN listeners' likelihood of the five possible responses changed by varying the duration of the word-final syllable. The post-hoc results revealed that long-duration patterns increased SN listeners' question-like responses and decreased their statement-like answers relative to stimuli with a short duration significantly ($\beta = .931$, $SE = .099$, $p < .0001$). A significant question recognition improvement was also observed for the CN group from the short to long-duration condition ($\beta = .303$, $SE = .069$, $p < .0001$). Nonetheless, this increase was less apparent in CN listeners than SN speakers, given their prior coefficients of the contrast between the short and long duration levels. Thus, our findings suggest that SN listeners were more sensitive than CN speakers to duration changes, although listeners of the two L1 groups could use to a different extent the duration cue to perceive intonation contrasts in Spanish (Fig. 3)

Further, the significant interaction between Duration \times f0 Change accords with previous speech perception studies, which showed that listeners could use the covariations between acoustic cues to help recognize the intended linguistic targets (Feng et al., 2019; Kuang & Cui, 2018; Yang & Sundara, 2019). Particularly, Fig. 4 reveals that CN and SN listeners could use a lower terminal pitch to hear the question when the duration of the final syllable was increased. Conversely, in the short duration condition, a higher final f0 contour was required for question recognitions, to compensate for the weakened duration cue. Both can be considered as an acoustical consequence of what is known as phonetic trading relations, which assume that changes in one acoustic cue can be counteracted by opposing changes in another cue so that phonetic quality is preserved (Repp, 1982). However, importantly, from the overall magnitude of slope changes in identification curves over the three duration levels by either L1 group (Fig. 4), SN listeners, who were more sensitive to the duration cue (c.f. previous paragraph for discussions), exhibited greater compensations for duration changes than CN speakers. This finding is consistent with

previous research (Nault & Munhall, 2020), which demonstrated that listeners with higher perceptual sensitivity were more likely to make bigger compensations for acoustic variations in auditory processing.

Fig. 3. Marginal effects of duration on each L1 Group while varying the final f0 contour in Experiment 1.

Fig. 4. Marginal effects of Age and Gender on each response level of Experiment 1, holding constant the f0 change at the median value of 80 Hz.

Regarding the effects of Age and Gender, Fig. 4 shows that when the listener was female and older, the predicted probability of question-like answers increased, whereas that of statement-like responses decreased. This result implies that older and female listeners were more likely to recognize a word as a question than males and younger ones under the same acoustic conditions. We posited that the age effect was likely because older listeners, particularly those of the CN group, had higher proficiencies in Spanish and were, thus, more capable of using acoustic cues for signaling question intonation. To validate this proposal, a further Kruskal-Wallis test by ranks was performed (Pohlert, 2014), and the results confirmed that there was a significant correlation between the Age and Spanish proficiency of CN listeners in Experiment 1 [$\chi^2(2) = 554.60, p < .0001$]. Thus, the effect of age on intonation perception might be considered as a perceptual benefit of higher language proficiencies in a non-native language. The last significant predictor of Experiment 1 was Stress Type, whose coefficients in Table 1 were negative in levels

1 and 2 and positive in levels 4 and 5. This result suggests that all else being equal, words with penultimate stress were more likely to be perceived by listeners as questions than those with final stress. The reasons listeners were more prone to perceive Spanish paroxytone words as questions are discussed in Section 5 below.

3.2 Results of Experiment 2

In Experiment 2, the predictors of Gender and Stimulus Order did not reach statistical significance and, thus, were excluded from the model. Results of the OGLM analysis (Table 2) demonstrated that the perception of the five possible sentence types was significantly predicted by Age [$\chi^2(1) = 8.45, p < .01$] and by the L1 Group \times f0 Change [$\chi^2(1) = 34.88, p < .001$] and f0 Change \times Intensity [$\chi^2(2) = 13.31, p < .01$] two-way interactions. Although the three-way interaction between L1 Group \times Intensity \times Stress Type was not statistically significant, we included it in the model because (a) the effects of Intensity [$\chi^2(2) = 16.80, p < .001$] and L1 Group [$\chi^2(1) = 26.20, p < .001$] was significantly modulated by Stress Type, and (b) the three-way interaction analysis can further help explain possible differences in intensity weighting between CN and SN listeners.

Table 2. Summary of the marginal effects in the OGLM model, fitted for Experiment 2 (coefficients and *t*-stat. *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$; ‘.’ $p < 0.1$.)

Predictor	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Age	-0.00488**	-0.01125**	-0.00667**	0.01456**	0.00825**
L1SN	0.13833***	0.22080***	0.04999*	-0.28048***	-0.12864***
f0×L1SN	-0.00030***	-0.00069***	-0.00041***	0.00090***	0.00051***
f0×70dB	-0.00004	-0.00010	-0.00006	0.00012	0.00007
f0×77dB	-0.00020***	-0.00045***	-0.00027***	0.00058***	0.00033***
L1SN×70dB	-0.01500.	-0.03680.	-0.02615	0.04654.	0.03135
L1SN×77dB	0.00327	0.00746	0.00425	-0.00967	-0.00531
L1SN×StressP	-0.02046**	-0.05025**	-0.03682*	0.06296**	0.04457*
StressP×70dB	-0.00197	-0.00456	-0.00276	0.00590	0.00339
StressP×77dB	-0.01604**	-0.03879*	-0.02695*	-0.04921**	0.03258*
StressP×70dB:L1SN	-0.00037	-0.00086	-0.00051	0.00111	0.00063
StressP×77dB×L1SN	-0.01426	-0.03488	-0.02510	0.04404	0.03019

Note: Levels 1–5, in order, signify the five possible responses in the perception test: statement, more statement than question, either statement or question, more question than statement, question. StressP signifies the one-word sentence with penultimate stress.

First, the positive coefficients of Age at levels 4 and 5 (Table 2) resonate with the data of Experiment 1, confirming that older listeners were more likely to recognize one-word sentences as yes-no questions than younger speakers. Again, this effect can be explained by the strong positive correlation between the Age and Spanish proficiency of CN listeners in Experiment 2 [$\chi^2(2) = 158.19, p < .0001$]. Similarly, the effect of f0 Change on the question-statement identification by either L1 Group accords with that in Experiment 1. For instance, Fig. 5 shows that the probability of question-like answers increased as the final f0 contour raised. Moreover, the negative coefficients of the SN Group at levels 4 and 5 (Table 2) indicate that CN speakers were significantly more likely to perceive one-word sentences as yes-no questions than SN listeners, probably because they categorized both mid- and high-level pitches as question intonation in Spanish.

Regarding the interaction between f0 Change \times L1 Group, their coefficients in Table 2 shows that the SN group had significantly steeper identification functions per f0 pitch than the SN group. This result strengthens the findings of Experiment 1, demonstrating that SN listeners

were more sensitive to f0 linear changes perceived as intonation than CN speakers. In addition, consistent with Experiment 1, results of Experiment 2 revealed that all else being equal, SN listeners needed higher terminal pitches to perceive questions than CN speakers, due to the influence of the three-way contrast of IP-final boundary tones in their L1 intonation system. For instance, as shown in Fig. 5, CN listeners needed a final f0 rise of 120 Hz for making “question” the most predicted sentence type, whereas SN listeners required a final f0 change greater than 140 Hz (particularly in the 63 dB and 70 dB conditions) for achieving the same response level in Experiment 2.

Fig. 5. Effect displays between L1 Group, f0 Change, and Intensity in Experiment 2.

In addition, similar to the f0 Change \times Duration interaction in Experiment 1, a significant trade-off relationship was found to operate between the two acoustic properties of f0 pitch \times Intensity. Specifically, Fig. 6 indicates that listeners could use a significantly lower f0 rise to make “question” the most predictive sentence type if the intensity was increased to the highest level (i.e., 77 dB). Additional evidence for the covariations of speech cues, as revealed by the positive coefficients of f0 Change \times 77 dB in levels 4 and 5 (Table 2), is that the slope of the identification curves on f0 pitch was significantly steeper at 77 dB than at 63 dB, implying that listeners could rely on fewer f0 cues for question recognitions when the intensity of word-final syllables increased. Again, this finding can be interpreted as acoustical consequences of phonetic trading relations or perceptual compensations for weakened speech cues (Nault & Munhall, 2020; Repp, 1982).

Before interpreting the three-way interaction, we examined the marginal effects of L1 Group in 70 dB and 77 dB conditions. Specifically, their coefficients in levels 4 and 5 (Table 2) indicate that SN listeners were more likely to perceive words as questions at 70 dB instead of 77 dB. This result may seem surprising at first sight, but the modulation of Stress Type explains it further. For the sake of simplicity, we discuss the relationship of the three variables with reference to Fig. 6. For instance, CN and SN listeners increased the likelihood of question-like responses in different ways when the word stress was on the penultimate syllable—paroxytone—and the intensity was manipulated from lower to higher levels. However, interestingly, the Intensity effect was not exhibited when listening to words with final stresses—oxytone. Moreover, as shown in Fig. 6, the SN group had a steady and significant stepwise increase in question identifications when the intensity of word-final syllables increased from 63 dB to 77 dB ($\beta = .462$, $SE = .155$, $p < .01$). By contrast, the effect of Intensity was weaker and irregular on the performance of CN listeners, as the coefficient of the contrast between 63 dB and 77 dB ($\beta = .222$, $SE = .098$, $p = .06$) reveals. Together, results of the three-way interaction indicate that the SN group relied more heavily on increased intensity to perceive paroxytone

words as questions, suggesting that SN listeners were more sensitive than CN speakers to the intensity cue.

Fig. 6. Effect displays for the three-way interaction between L1 Group, Intensity, and Stress Type in levels 4 (more statement than question) and 5 (question) of Experiment 2.

3.3 Estimation of model performance

The log loss metric is among the most selective functions to estimate the quality of probabilistic predictions; it works particularly well when there are multi-class classification problems (Brown, 2020). Therefore, to assess the predictive accuracy of the models, log loss values were computed on the testing set using the *mlogLoss* function from the *ModelMetrics* package for R (Hunt, 2020). Log loss of the OGLM model was calculated as 1.0483 and 1.0286 for Experiments 1 and 2, respectively.

Since log loss measures testing error and model uncertainty, the lower the value, the better the prediction. A model considered good should have a log loss that is at least less than the “dumb” or non-informative log loss. The “dumb” log loss was calculated assuming the number of classes (M) was uniformly distributed in the data (Brown, 2020). In this study, we have $M=5$ response levels, each with a 20% chance of occurrence. Hence, the “dumb” log loss of the model, fitted for Experiments 1 and 2, was calculated as in Equation (1):

$$\log loss = -\ln\left(\frac{1}{M}\right) = -\ln\left(\frac{1}{5}\right) = \ln(5) = 1.6094. \quad (1)$$

However, in fact, the five classes of the outcome variable did not occur equally in the data; thus, the non-informative log loss of the model was further computed, assuming a specified non-uniform distribution of listeners’ responses. The non-informative log loss for both models was calculated by specifying the probability of each class. For instance, Experiment 1 has 21.77%, 16.49%, 10.88%, 24.13%, and 26.74% responses for “statement,” “more statement than question,” “either statement or question,” “more question than statement,” and “question.” Thus, the non-informative log loss for the model of Experiment 1 was calculated as in Equation (2):

$$\begin{aligned} \log loss &= -\left(0.2117\ln(0.2117) + 0.1649\ln(0.1649) + 0.1088\ln(0.1088)\right. \\ &\quad \left.+ 0.2413\ln(0.2413) + 0.2674\ln(0.2674)\right). \quad (2) \\ &= 1.5662 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, the non-informative log loss for the model of Experiment 2 was calculated to be

1.6113. Overall, the average log loss for the two models was effectively reduced to 1.0483 and 1.0286 relative to the “dumb” and non-informative log loss. Therefore, the models for these two experiments can be considered accurate and predictive, outperforming “dumb” and non-informative models.

4.0 Discussion

The present study investigated the perceptual weighting of the three acoustic cues— f_0 , duration, and intensity—in perceiving Spanish intonation contrasts by CN and SN listeners. The stimuli were created by manipulating the f_0 contours progressively from falling to rising directions while changing the duration or intensity of word-final syllables. Unlike prior studies that usually provided two opposite perceptual options (i.e., statement vs. question), we used a five-point Likert response scale to capture listeners’ perceptions more precisely.

In general, the results of the two auditory experiments demonstrated that the f_0 contour was the primary cue for both CN and SN listeners in the question-statement identification of Peninsular Spanish, followed by the duration changes. The parametric variation of the intensity seems to be the least contributing acoustic factor, being used most variably by listeners in the prosodic evaluation of intonation categories. Beyond this cross-linguistic commonality of cue ranking, listeners of the two language groups differed in their use of the f_0 -, duration-, and intensity modulation patterns for perceiving intonation contrasts and in the compensatory behavior for dealing with the covariations of multiple acoustic cues.

4.1 *The role of f_0 contour in intonation perception*

The first distinction is that SN listeners perceived yes-no questions using significantly higher final f_0 contours than CN listeners, especially when the value of secondary cues (i.e., duration or intensity) was reduced. This finding confirms our predictions, consistent with Feng et al. (2019), where English L1 listeners used a significantly higher offset f_0 frequency for question identifications than Chinese L2 speakers, except in the long-duration condition. The situation may be attributed to native (SN) listeners being more capable than non-native (CN) speakers in compensating for the weakened secondary cues and f_0 loss caused by the pitch synthesis because of their broader linguistic experience with Spanish. Moreover, the exact mapping between f_0 levels and Spanish intonation categories may have required SN listeners to use higher terminal pitches to signal questions to distinguish them from epistemically biased statements encoded with mid-level tones (i.e., uncertainty statements expressed with !H% or statements of obvious expressed with L!H%). However, intonation types in Chinese are not determined by the surface f_0 contours at the end of the sentence. Thus, CN listeners may interpret any IP-final boundary tone not strictly low (i.e., !H% or L!H%) as high, thereby classifying it in a question category. The tendency of CN listeners to categorize both mid- and high-level tones as questions also explained their higher likelihood of question identifications than SN speakers during this process.

Apart from auditory categorization differences, the significantly steeper identification curves exhibited by the SN group in the two experiments suggested that SN listeners were more sensitive than CN speakers to f_0 linear transitions perceived as intonation. Thus, the previously proposed tonal language benefit may be significant only in specific dimensions of pitch events, such as naturally-produced f_0 contrastive patterns that vary phonetically like lexical tones (i.e., Chandrasekaran et al., 2007; Deroche et al., 2019; Hallé et al., 2004; Ortega-Llebaria & Wu, 2021) but not in f_0 linear sweeps perceived at the sentence-intonation level. Recent studies supporting this idea can be found in Chien et al. (2020). Specifically, the authors demonstrated that pitch processing as intonation involved bilateral cortical areas, generalized to listeners of tonal (Chinese) and non-tonal (German) languages despite the different realizations of

intonation in their L1. By contrast, the processing of f0 pitch as lexical tone engaged semantic areas specific to Chinese speakers, in addition to the left-hemispheric phonological system activated by tonal and non-tonal language groups (Chien et al., 2020).

From prior neurobehavioral findings, CN and SN listeners should have comparable pitch performance in this study because they had the same neural network for intonation processing. However, contrary to predictions, CN listeners showed lower sensitivity to f0 pitch perceived as intonation than SN speakers probably because they were exposed to a non-native environment (unlike the Chinese auditory stimuli used in Chien et al., [2020]), where they had limited experience in perceiving f0 contours along the lines of language-specific and well-defined intonation categories. Moreover, the functional view explains that if some phonetic cues are exploited in one dimension of grammar, they will not be used to the same degree in another area of phonology (Gandour et al., 1995; Liang & Heuven, 2007; Seddoh, 2002). Thus, the f0 pitch in Mandarin Chinese having a dual linguistic function (e.g., tone and intonation) may have influenced CN listeners' auditory processing of different pitch events. Accordingly, Chen (2005), Gussenhoven and Chen (2000), and Liang and Heuven (2007) argued that the preference of tonal language listeners to primarily perceive the f0 information bearing on word meanings (i.e., lexical tone) was a critical factor for their decreased sensitivity to f0 variations processed as intonation. By extension, we posit that CN listeners' extra effort in processing the pitch patterns of non-native lexical stress may have induced their weaker ability to decode the f0 cues at the sentence-intonation level.

4.2 The role of secondary cues in intonation perception

It is interesting that in addition to f0 contour, the duration was also a salient cue for both CN and SN listeners during question-statement identification. Long-duration patterns could significantly increase the likelihood of question responses for both L1 groups relative to stimuli with a short duration. However, compared to the SN group, the overall magnitude of improvements over the three duration levels was smaller in the CN group, confirming our predictions that non-native (CN) listeners were less sensitive than native (SN) speakers to the duration modulations in Spanish sentence types. A similar scenario was observed regarding the perceptual weighting of the intensity cue. Only SN listeners were sensitive to intensity variations in paroxytone words, whereas the performance of CN listeners was not influenced by changes in intensity when perceiving paroxytone or oxytone words. These cross-linguistic differences in intonation cue weighting between native and non-native listeners generally are consistent with Feng et al. (2019), although the authors did not find a significant effect of the duration or intensity cue on the question-statement recognition by Chinese learners of English. More so, comparing the statistical significance of two secondary cues (i.e., duration and intensity), this study posited that intensity was a less prominent cue than duration in question-statement identification by either L1 group, which was used variably by listeners per the stress position of the word.

Similar perceptual compensation explanations are adopted here for the greater reliance of SN listeners on those secondary cues (i.e., duration or intensity). Since pitch contours synthesized in this study differed from intonation patterns of Spanish statements and questions produced in natural speaking environments (not wholly linear at the end of the utterance), listeners may increase the weight of other secondary cues to compensate for the loss of f0 pitch and enhance their perceptual decisions (Feng et al., 2019). Nonetheless, SN listeners may know how to compensate for acoustic changes in speech better than CN speakers because they have more extensive experience with the phonetic patterns of Spanish intonation categories. Beyond the differences in compensatory ability, the cue weighting paradigm in CN listeners' native prosodic system may induce their reduced sensitivity to duration and intensity cues. Since f0 pitch plays an overwhelming role in Mandarin, CN listeners may be less likely to attend to those less prominent acoustic features when identifying an intonation category, especially in non-native environments (e.g., Chang & Yao, 2007; Feng et al., 2019; Jiao & Xu, 2019). Overall, the

findings of perceptual cue weighting are consistent with previous research (e.g., Feng et al., 2019; Holt & Lotto, 2006; Kuang & Cui, 2018; Meng et al., 2020; Peng et al., 2012), where listeners from different language backgrounds differ in the way they use multiple sources of acoustic cues to specify the best exemplar of speech categories.

4.3 The implications of the trade-off relationship in speech perception

From the above discussion, it is clear that different acoustic cues can contribute to a different extent to the listener's judgments for a phonological contrast since listeners' attention is selective (Kuang & Cui, 2018). But, how do listeners integrate and coordinate the weighting of these cues to arrive at an overall estimate of the intonation category? A clue to answering this question may lie in the significant interaction effects between primary and secondary cues on the question-statement recognition. In specific, our study revealed that the effect of f0 contour was strongly covaried with the duration or intensity cue during the perceptual process. Since f0, duration, and intensity are relevant cues for identifying the question-statement contrast, the attenuation in one acoustic dimension of them could be compensated by providing greater contributions from the other so that the original percept can be recovered. This trade-off relationship between two or more acoustic properties is consistent with the core idea of phonetic trading relations proposed by Repp (1982). Similar phenomena have been widely documented in identifications of phonetic segments, such as ongoing sound changes in Southern Yi (c.f. tense vs. lax register in Kuang & Cui, 2018), CV syllable distinctions in English (c.f. *ba* vs. *wa* in Boardman et al., 1994), and stop-consonant voicing contrasts in American English (c.f. Holt et al., 2001; Jacewicz et al., 2009).

Evidence from this study and many other works (e.g., Feng et al., 2019; Hodgson & Miller, 1996; Holt et al., 2001; Holt & Lotto, 2006; Kuang & Cui, 2018; Peng et al., 2012) has shown that listeners are sensitive to the multiplicity and covariations of acoustic-phonetic information for a given speech category, and can use a compensatory strategy actively to ensure the success of perceiving an intended linguistic category. However, Hodgson and Miller (1996) argued that the auditory compensation was contingent upon listeners who are sensitive to the co-varying cues that are consistently correlated with the recognition of a given phonetic segment. This notion has been supported by recent empirical studies (Nault and Munhall, 2020; Villacorta et al., 2007), which further demonstrated that listeners with higher perceptual sensitivity were more likely to make greater compensations for acoustic variations in speech. Thus, in this study, native (SN) listeners were more susceptible to phonetic trading relations and better at compensating for acoustic changes in Spanish sentence types, probably because of their greater auditory sensitivity than non-native (CN) listeners to acoustic-phonetic properties encoded in their L1 intonation system. These findings may serve as a good example of phonetic trading relations being used as a tool to assess listeners' sensitivity to multiple acoustic cues of speech.

4.4 The role of individual and prosodic features in intonation perception

In line with our prior hypothesis, question-statement identification in Spanish is not solely determined by listeners' native language background but is also modulated by individual differences in age and gender. Older and female listeners were more likely to recognize one-word sentences as yes-no questions than younger and male speakers. Given that there was a strong correlation between the age of CN listeners and their proficiency in Spanish, the age effect could be alternatively explained by older CN listeners who were more proficient in Spanish had long-time exposure to distributions of acoustic features in target phonetic environments, thereby being more capable of using multiple cues for recognizing question-statement contrasts. Nevertheless, this relationship between the two variables is likely limited to the CN group. Thus, further research is needed to verify this correlation and examine the respective age effect on intonation perception for native and non-native listeners. Moreover, women having a higher likelihood of question identifications probably can be attributed to their

higher pragmatic skills than men in speech communication (evaluated by the communication subscale of the Autism-Spectrum Quotient (Baron-Cohen et al., 2001) by Bishop et al. [2020]), which may make them more sensitive to the mapping between prosodic patterns and pragmatic meanings. Notably, this gender effect was significant only in Experiment 1, whereas in Experiment 2, it did not reach statistical significance. Therefore, further experimental investigations with an equal number of male and female listeners are required to better understand this gender difference in the prosodic evaluation of intonation categories.

A final interesting finding of this study is listeners' perception performance is also subject to prosodic structures of the words, such as the stress position. Paroxytone words were more likely to be perceived as yes-no questions than oxytone words in Experiment 1, likely because the paroxytone was the most frequent and unmarked stress pattern in Spanish that adult listeners always had the least challenge in processing it during perception (Defior & Serrano, 2017; Roca, 2019). Moreover, the potential f_0 conflicts between stress and intonation bearing on the last syllable of oxytone words may have increased CN listeners' challenge in perceiving the f_0 pitch at the sentence-intonation level. In Experiment 2, the effect of intensity amplification was significant only for the perception of paroxytone words, but not for oxytone words. Although the reasons for this perceptual difference in stress type are not wholly understood, we speculate that the acoustic interference of the stress on the last syllable may be a plausible cause for listeners' irregular use of intensity to perceive oxytone words. Future relevant studies are needed to validate the effect of stress on intensity perception.

4.5 Limitations and future directions

Several limitations and emergent future directions are as follows. First, even though f_0 contour, duration, and intensity are the most salient cues for perceiving intonation, recognizing question-statement contrasts is not limited to these acoustic properties. Other contextual variables such as speaking rate and phonetic environment may also play a role in the specification of the best exemplars of intonation categories. Second, this study used one-word sentences to examine the cue weighting differences between CN and SN listeners in question-statement identification. Thus, whether these results can be generalized to sentences with more than one stressed word remains to be tested. Third, although the findings of this study support the existence of a phonetic trading relationship between primary (i.e., f_0) and secondary (i.e., duration or intensity) cues, it remains unclear whether this relationship exists between the duration and intensity cues. Hence, future studies with appropriate experimental designs (e.g., stimuli with covariations in duration and intensity) can bridge the limitations. Additional limitations include the imbalance between male and female listeners, which may limit the powers of the present sample and explain the nonsignificant gender effect in Experiment 2. Finally, despite positing that the acoustic interference of final stress may induce perceptual differences in the two stress types, how stress and intonation are encoded in parallel via changes in acoustic cues and how stress processing affects the perception of acoustic patterns as intonation remains to be elucidated.

5.0 Conclusion

This study examined the perceptual weighting of the three acoustic cues— f_0 , duration, and intensity—in Spanish question-statement identification by CN and SN listeners. The overall findings revealed cross-linguistic commonalities and dissociations of intonation processing between tonal and non-tonal language listeners. While CN and SN listeners could use f_0 and duration cues to different extents to recognize intonation contrasts, only SN listeners were sensitive to intensity modulations of paroxytone words. More importantly, SN listeners showed a higher sensitivity to the acoustic changes of f_0 pitch, duration, and intensity than CN speakers, probably because of their superior compensatory capacity and broader linguistic experience with Spanish prosody. The greater pitch sensitivity exhibited by SN listeners during intonation

perception tentatively rejects the general hypothesis of tonal language benefit in pitch perception by showing that the f0 advantage of CN listeners is not generalized to all dimensions of pitch patterns. Moreover, beyond listeners' L1 background, the cue weighting paradigms of CN and SN listeners could be influenced by specific individual and prosodic features. Finally, the trade-off relationship between primary (i.e., f0) and secondary (i.e., duration and intensity) cues confirms that, rather than a single f0 modulation, the perception of intonation contrasts involves the dynamic interplay of multidimensional acoustic cues (Levis, 1999; Ma et al., 2008; Niebuhr, 2007).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Peizhu Shang: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Writing -Original Draft, Visualization. **Paolo Roseano:** Methodology, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Resources. **Wendy Elvira-García:** Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Resources, Visualization.

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Appendix A. Detailed manipulation values of the three acoustic cues in the two one-word sentences.

Appendix B. Results of pairwise comparisons of... **to be done.**

Appendix C. The schematic representation of the intensity manipulation for the one-word sentence “Alcalá,” keeping the original pitch contour of the statement (The green, blue, and red intensity curves in the final vowel have a value of 63 dB, 70 dB, and 77dB, respectively.)

Reference

- Abrudan, I.-N., Pop, C.-M., & Lazăr, P.-S. (2020). Using a General Ordered Logit Model to Explain the Influence of Hotel Facilities, General and Sustainability-Related, on Customer Ratings. *Sustainability*, 12(21), 9302. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12219302>.
- Baron-Cohen, S., Wheelwright, S., Hill, J., Raste, Y., & Plumb, I. (2001). The “Reading the Mind in the Eyes” test revised version: A study with normal adults, and adults with Asperger syndrome or high-functioning autism. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 42(2), 241–251. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/11280420/>.

- Bidelman, G. M., Gandour, J. T., & Krishnan, A. (2011). Cross-domain effects of music and language experience on the representation of pitch in the human auditory brainstem. *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience*, 23(2), 425–434. <https://doi.org/10.1162/jocn.2009.21362>.
- Bidelman, G. M., Hutka, S., & Moreno, S. (2013). Tone language speakers and musicians share enhanced perceptual and cognitive abilities for musical pitch: evidence for bidirectionality between the domains of language and music. *PloS One*, 8(4), e60676. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0060676>.
- Bidelman, G. M., Krishnan, A., & Gandour, J. T. (2011). Enhanced brainstem encoding predicts musicians' perceptual advantages with pitch. *European Journal of Neuroscience*, 33(3), 530–538. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-9568.2010.07527.x>.
- Bishop, J., Kuo, G., & Kim, B. (2020). Phonology, phonetics, and signal-extrinsic factors in the perception of prosodic prominence: Evidence from Rapid Prosody Transcription. *Journal of Phonetics*, 82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wocn.2020.100977>.
- Boardman, I., Grossberg, S., & Cohen, M. (1994). *Neural Dynamics of Phonetic Trading Relations for Variable-Rate CV Syllables*. Boston University Center for Adaptive Systems and Department of Cognitive and Neural Systems. <https://hdl.handle.net/2144/2175>.
- Boersma, P., & Weenink, D. (2020). Praat: doing phonetics by computer [Computer program] (Version 5.3.82). Retrieved from <http://www.praat.org>.
- Bolinger, D. (1978). Intonation across languages. In Joseph H. Greenberg (Ed.), *Universals of Human Language Volume 2: Phonology* (pp. 471–524). Stanford University Press.
- Brown, M. K. W. (2020). *Evaluating an Ordinal Output using Data Modeling, Algorithmic Modeling, and Numerical Analysis*. Master thesis. Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Murray State University. <https://digitalcommons.murraystate.edu/etd/168>.
- Carroll, N. (2018). OglmX: A Package for Estimation of Ordered Generalized Linear Models . R package version 3.0.0.0. <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/oglmX/index.html>.
- Chandrasekaran, B., Krishnan, A., & Gandour, J. T. (2007). Experience-dependent neural plasticity is sensitive to shape of pitch contours. *Neuroreport*, 18(18), 1963–1967. <https://doi.org/10.1097/wnr.0b013e3282f213c5>.
- Chang, C. B., & Yao, Y. (2007). Tone production in whispered Mandarin. In *16th International Congress of Phonetic Sciences* (pp. 1085–1088). <https://escholarship.org/content/qt1581q7qr/qt1581q7qr.pdf>.
- Chang, S. E. (2013). Effects of Fundamental Frequency and Duration Variation on the Perception of South Kyungsang Korean Tones. *Language and Speech*, 56(2), 211–228. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0023830912443951>.
- Chen, S. H. (2005). The effects of tones on speaking frequency and intensity ranges in Mandarin and Min dialects. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 117(5), 3225–3230. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.1872312>.
- Chien, P. J., Friederici, A. D., Hartwigsen, G., & Sammler, D. (2020). Neural correlates of intonation and lexical tone in tonal and non-tonal language speakers. *Human Brain Mapping*, 41(7), 1842–1858. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.24916>.
- Clayards, M. (2018). Differences in cue weights for speech perception are correlated for individuals within and across contrasts. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 144(3), EL172–EL177. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.5052025>.
- Defior, S., & Serrano, F. (2017). Learning to Read Spanish. In Verhoeven, L., & Perfetti, C. (Eds.), *Learning to Read across Languages and Writing Systems* (pp. 243–269). Cambridge University Press. https://assets.cambridge.org/97811070/95885/frontmatter/9781107095885_frontmatter.pdf.
- Deroche, M. L. D., Lu, H. P., Kulkarni, A. M., Caldwell, M., Barrett, K. C., Peng, S. C., Limb, C. J., Lin, Y. S., & Chatterjee, M. (2019). A tonal-language benefit for pitch in normally-hearing and cochlear-implanted children. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-36393-1>.
- Divenyi, P., Greenberg, S., & Meyer, G. (Eds.) (2006). *Dynamics of speech production and perception* (Vol. 374). Amsterdam: Ios Press. <https://ebooks.iospress.nl/ISBN/978-1-58603-666-9>.

- Doherty, C. P., West, W. C., Dilley, L. C., Shattuck-Hufnagel, S., & Caplan, D. (2004). Question/statement judgments: an fMRI study of intonation processing. *Human Brain Mapping, 23*(2), 85–98. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1002%2Fhbm.20042>.
- Estebas-Vilaplana, E., & Prieto, P. (2010). Castilian Spanish intonation. In P. Prieto & P. Roseano (Eds.), *Transcription of intonation of the Spanish language* (pp. 17–48). München: LINCOM Europa. http://prosodia.upf.edu/home/arxiu/activitats/4th_workshop/protegit/transcription_intonation_spanish_prieto_roseano_lincom.pdf.
- Face, T. L. (2005). F0 Peak Height and the Perception of Sentence Type in Castilian Spanish. *Revista Internacional de Lingüística Iberoamericana, 3*(2), 49–65. <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/articulo?codigo=1342296>.
- Face, T. L. (2007). The role of intonational cues in the perception of declaratives and absolute interrogatives in Castilian Spanish. *Estudios de Fonética Experimental, 16*, 186–225.
- Face, T. L. (2011). *Perception of Castilian Spanish Intonation: Implications for Intonational Phonology*. München: LINCOM Europa.
- Face, T. L., & Prieto, P. (2007). Rising accents in Castilian Spanish: A revision of Sp_ToBI. *Journal of Portuguese Linguistics, 6*(1), 117–146.
- Félix-Brasdefer, J. C. (2010). Data collection methods in speech act performance. In Flor, A. M., & Juan, E. U. (Eds.), *Speech Act Performance: Theoretical, Empirical and Methodological Issues* (Vol. 26, pp. 69–82). Amsterdam: John Benjamins. <https://benjamins.com/catalog/llt.26>.
- Feng, J., Tao, S., Wu, X., Alsbury, K., & Liu, C. (2019). The effects of amplitude and duration on the perception of English statements vs questions for native English and Chinese listeners. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America, 145*(5), EL449–EL455. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.5109046>.
- Friederici, A. D. (2011). The brain basis of language processing: from structure to function. *Physiological Reviews, 91*(4), 1357–1392. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.00006.2011>.
- Gandour, J., Larsen, J., Dechongkit, S., Ponglorpisit, S., & Khunadorn, F. (1995). Speech prosody in affective contexts in Thai patients with right hemisphere lesions. *Brain and Language, 51*(3), 422–443. <https://doi.org/10.1006/brln.1995.1069>.
- Gandour, J. T. (2009). Neural substrates underlying the perception of linguistic prosody. In Gussenhoven, C., & Riad, T. (Eds.), *Experimental Studies in Word and Sentence Prosody* (pp. 3–26). Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/9783110207576/html>.
- Gussenhoven, C., & Chen, A. (2000). Universal and language-specific effects in the perception of question intonation. In *6th International Conference on Spoken Language Processing* (pp. 91–94). https://www.isca-speech.org/archive/pdfs/icslp_2000/gussenhoven00_icslp.pdf.
- Hallé, P. A., Chang, Y. C., & Best, C. T. (2004). Identification and discrimination of Mandarin Chinese tones by Mandarin Chinese vs. French listeners. *Journal of Phonetics, 32*(3), 395–421. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0095-4470\(03\)00016-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0095-4470(03)00016-0).
- Hattori, K., & Iverson, P. (2010). Examination of the relationship between L2 perception and production: an investigation of English/r/-l/perception and production by adult Japanese speakers. In *Second Language Studies: Acquisition, Learning, Education and Technology*, 1–4.
- Haverkate, H. (2006). Aspectos pragmatolingüísticos de la interrogación en español con atención especial a las secuencias de preguntas. *Cultura, Lengua y Representación, 3*(3), 27–40. <https://www.e-revistas.uji.es/index.php/clr/article/view/1317>.
- Hodgson, P., & Miller, J. L. (1996). Internal structure of phonetic categories: Evidence for within-category trading relations. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America, 100*(1), 565–576. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1121/1.415867>.
- Holt, L. L., Lotto, A. J., & Kluender, K. R. (2001). Influence of fundamental frequency on stop-consonant voicing perception: A case of learned covariation or auditory enhancement?

- Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 109(2), 764–774. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.1339825>.
- Holt, L. L., & Lotto, A. J. (2006). Cue weighting in auditory categorization: Implications for first and second language acquisition. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 119(5), 3059–3071. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.2188377>.
- Hunt, T. (2020). ModelMetrics: Rapid calculation of model metrics. R package version 1.2.2.2. <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/ModelMetrics/ModelMetrics.pdf>.
- Jacewicz, E., Fox, R. A., & Lyle, S. (2009). Variation in stop consonant voicing in two regional varieties of American English. *Journal of the International Phonetic Association*, 39(3), 313–334. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0025100309990156>.
- Jiao, L., & Xu, Y. (2019). Whispered Mandarin has no production-enhanced cues for tone and intonation. *Lingua*, 218, 24–37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lingua.2018.01.004>.
- Kassambara, A. (2018). *Machine learning essentials: Practical guide in R*. Sthda. <https://www.datanovia.com/en/product/machine-learning-essentials-practical-guide-in-r/?url=/5-bookadvisor/54-machine-learning-essentials/>.
- Kreitewolf, J., Friederici, A. D., & von Kriegstein, K. (2014). Hemispheric lateralization of linguistic prosody recognition in comparison to speech and speaker recognition. *NeuroImage*, 102, 332–344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2014.07.038>.
- Krishnan, A., Gandour, J. T., & Bidelman, G. M. (2010). The effects of tone language experience on pitch processing in the brainstem. *Journal of Neurolinguistics*, 23(1), 81–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneuroling.2009.09.001>.
- Kuang, J., & Cui, A. (2018). Relative cue weighting in production and perception of an ongoing sound change in Southern Yi. *Journal of Phonetics*, 71, 194–214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wocn.2018.09.002>.
- Ladd, D. R. (1996). *Intonational phonology*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511808814>.
- Lee, H., Politzer-Ahles, S., & Jongman, A. (2013). Speakers of tonal and non-tonal Korean dialects use different cue weightings in the perception of the three-way laryngeal stop contrast. *Journal of Phonetics*, 41(2), 117–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wocn.2012.12.002>.
- Levis, J. M. (1999). Intonation in theory and practice, revisited. *TESOL Quarterly*, 33(1), 37–63. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3588190>.
- Liang, J., & Heuven, V. J. (2007). Chinese tone and intonation perceived by L1 and L2 listeners. In C. Gussenhoven & T. Riad (Eds.), *Experimental Studies in Word and Sentence Prosody Volume 2* (pp. 27–62). Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110207576.1.27>.
- Lieberman, P. (1967). *Intonation, perception, and language*. M.I.T. Research Monograph, 38, xiii, 210.
- Lin, M. (2018). *Tone and intonation processing: From ambiguous acoustic signal to linguistic representation* (Doctoral dissertation). Leiden University. <https://hdl.handle.net/1887/66615>.
- Liu, P., & Pell, M. D. (2012). Recognizing vocal emotions in Mandarin Chinese: A validated database of Chinese vocal emotional stimuli. *Behavior Research Methods*, 44(4), 1042–1051. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-012-0203-3>.
- Ma, J. K. Y., Ciocca, V., & Whitehill, T. L. (2008). Acoustic cues for the perception of intonation in Cantonese. In *9th Annual Conference of the International Speech Communication Association* (pp. 520–523). https://www.isca-speech.org/archive_v0/archive_papers/interspeech_2008/i08_0520.pdf.
- Ma, J. K.-Y., Ciocca, V., & Whitehill, T. L. (2011). The perception of intonation questions and statements in Cantonese. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 129(2), 1012–1023. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.3531840>.
- Matthews, W. J., Stewart, N., & Wearden, J. H. (2011). Stimulus Intensity and the Perception of Duration. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, 37(1), 303–313. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0019961>.

- Meng, Y., Zhang, J., Liu, S., & Wu, C. (2020). Influence of different acoustic cues in L1 lexical tone on the perception of L2 lexical stress using principal component analysis: an ERP study. *Experimental Brain Research*, 238(6), 1489–1498. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00221-020-05823-w>.
- Morrow, K., & Liu, C. (2013, June). Intonation perception in English: Effects of stimulus amplitude and listeners' language background. In *Proceedings of Meetings on Acoustics* (Vol. 19, 1–5). Acoustical Society of America. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.4800156>.
- Nault, D. R., & Munhall, K. G. (2020). Individual variability in auditory feedback processing: Responses to real-time formant perturbations capacity and their relation to perceptual acuity. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 148(6), 3709–3721. <https://doi.org/10.1121/10.0002923>.
- Niebuhr, O. (2007). Categorical perception in intonation: A matter of signal dynamics? In *INTERSPEECH 8th Annual Conference of the International Speech Communication Association* (pp. 642–645). https://www.isca-speech.org/archive/pdfs/interspeech_2007/niebuhr07_interspeech.pdf.
- Ortega-Llebaria, M., Nemogá, M., & Presson, N. (2017). Long-term experience with a tonal language shapes the perception of intonation in English words: How Chinese-English bilinguals perceive “Rose?” vs. “Rose.” *Bilingualism*, 20(2), 367–383. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1366728915000723>.
- Ortega-Llebaria, M., & Wu, Z. (2021). Chinese-English Speakers' Perception of Pitch in Their Non-Tonal Language: Reinterpreting English as a Tonal-Like Language. *Language and Speech*, 64(2), 467–487. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0023830919894606>
- Patel, R., & Grigos, M. I. (2006). Acoustic characterization of the question–statement contrast in 4-, 7- and 11-year-old children. *Speech Communication*, 48(10), 1308–1318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.specom.2006.06.007>.
- Peng, S. C., Chatterjee, M., & Lu, N. (2012). Acoustic Cue Integration in Speech Intonation Recognition With Cochlear Implants. *Trends in Amplification*, 16(2), 67–82. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1084713812451159>.
- Pohlert, T. (2014). *The pairwise multiple comparison of mean ranks package (PMCMR)*. R package. <https://cran.microsoft.com/snapshot/2015-03-19/web/packages/PMCMR/vignettes/PMCMR.pdf>
- Repp, B. H. (1982). Phonetic trading relations and context effects: new experimental evidence for a speech mode of perception. *Psychological Bulletin*, 92(1), 81–110. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0033-2909.92.1.81>.
- Ripley, B., Venables, B., Bates, D. M., Hornik, K., Gebhardt, A., Firth, D., & Ripley, M. B. (2013). Package ‘mass.’ *Cran R*, 538, 113–120. <ftp://192.218.129.11/pub/CRAN/web/packages/MASS/MASS.pdf>.
- Roca, I. (2019). Spanish Word Stress: an updated multidimensional account. In Goedemans, R., Heinz, J., & van der Hulst, H. (Eds.), *The Study of Word Stress and Accent: Theories, Methods and Data* (pp. 256–292). Cambridge University Press.
- Rodero, E. (2011). Intonation and emotion: influence of pitch levels and contour type on creating emotions. *Journal of Voice*, 25(1), e25–e34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvoice.2010.02.002>.
- Romera Barrios, L., Fernández-Planas, A. M., Salcioli Guidi, V., Carrera Sabaté, J., & Montes de Oca, D. R. (2007). Una muestra del español de Barcelona en el marco AMPER. *Estudios de Fonética Experimental*, 16(16), 147–184. <https://raco.cat/index.php/EFE/article/view/140051>.
- Ryalls, J., Dorze, G. Le, Lever, N., Ouellet, L., & Larfeuil, C. (1994). The effects of age and sex on speech intonation and duration for matched statements and questions in French. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 95(4), 2274–2276. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.408639>
- Seddoh, S. A. (2002). How discrete or independent are ‘‘affective prosody’’ and ‘‘linguistic prosody’’? *Aphasiology*, 16(7), 683–692. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02687030143000861>.
- So, C. K., & Best, C. T. (2010). Cross-language perception of non-native tonal contrasts: Effects of native phonological and phonetic influences. *Language and Speech*, 53(2), 273–293. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0023830909357156>.

- Steppling, M. L., & Montgomery, A. A. (2002). Perception and production of rise-fall intonation in American English. *Perception and Psychophysics*, *64*(3), 451–461. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03194717>.
- Syntrillium Software Corporation. (2003). Cool Edit Pro. Version 2.1. Phoenix.
- R Core Team (2021). R: A language and environment for statistical computing. Version 1.4.1103 Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. Available at: www.R-project.org.
- Tillman, G., Benders, T., Brown, S. D., & Ravenzwaaij, D. van. (2017). An evidence accumulation model of acoustic cue weighting in vowel perception. *Journal of Phonetics*, *61*, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wocn.2016.12.001>.
- Toscano, J. C., & McMurray, B. (2010). Cue integration with categories: Weighting acoustic cues in speech using unsupervised learning and distributional statistics. In *Cognitive Science* (Vol. 34, Issue 3, pp. 434–464). <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1551-6709.2009.01077.x>.
- Tsukada, K. (2018). The Perception of Mandarin Lexical Tones by Native Speakers of Burmese. *Language and Speech*, *62*(4), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0023830918806550>.
- Villacorta, V. M., Perkell, J. S., & Guenther, F. H. (2007). Sensorimotor adaptation to feedback perturbations of vowel acoustics and its relation to perception. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, *122*(4), 2306–2319. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.2773966>.
- Wichmann, A., & Blakemore, D. (2006). The prosody-pragmatics interface. *Journal of Pragmatics*, *38*(10), 1537–1541. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pragma.2006.02.009>.
- Williams, R. (2016). Understanding and interpreting generalized ordered logit models. *Journal of Mathematical Sociology*, *40*(1), 7–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0022250X.2015.1112384>.
- Xu, Y., Gandour, J. T., & Francis, A. L. (2006). Effects of language experience and stimulus complexity on the categorical perception of pitch direction. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, *120*(2), 1063–1074. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.2213572>.
- Yuan, J. (2004). *Intonation in Mandarin Chinese: Acoustics, perception, and computational modeling* (Doctoral dissertation). New York: Cornell University.
- Yuan, J. (2006). Mechanisms of question intonation in Mandarin. In M. B. Huo Q., C. ES., & L. H. (Eds.), *International Symposium on Chinese Spoken Language Processing* (pp. 19–30). Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 4274. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/11939993_7.
- Yuan, J. (2011). Perception of intonation in Mandarin Chinese. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, *130*(6), 4063–4069. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.3651818>.
- Zarate-Sandez, G. A., Morales-Front, A., & Sanz, C. (2015). *Perception and production of intonation among English-Spanish bilingual speakers at different proficiency levels* (Doctoral dissertation). Washington: Georgetown University. <https://repository.library.georgetown.edu/handle/10822/761510>.
- Zatorre, R. J., & Gandour, J. T. (2008). Neural specializations for speech and pitch: Moving beyond the dichotomies. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *363*(1493), 1087–1104. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2007.2161>.